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Trust in the Judicial System in the Italian Regions

Between 2011 and 2022 it grew by 5.8%

Istat calculates trust in the judicial system in the Italian regions. The indicator is defined as an average score of trust in the justice system (on a scale from 0 to 10) expressed by people aged 14 and over. The data takes into consideration the period between 2011 and 2022 for the Italian regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of trust in the judicial system in 2022. Campania is in first place by value of trust in the judicial system in 2022 with a value of 5.3 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 5.2 units and from Lazio with a value of 5.1 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont, Emilia Romagna and Tuscany with a value of 4.8 units. Lombardy and Veneto close the ranking with a value of 4.5 units and Valle d'Aosta with a value of 4.2 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the value of trust in the judicial system between 2011 and 2022. Abruzzo is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the value of trust in the judicial system with a value equal to +20.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.00 units up to a value of 4.80 units or corresponding to a variation of 0.80 units. Basilicata follows with a variation corresponding to an amount of 13.33% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.50 units up to a value of 5.10 units or equal to an amount of 0.60 units. Campania is in third place with a variation equal to +12.77% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.70 units up to a value of 5.30 units or corresponding to a variation of 0.60 units. In the middle of the table is Emilia Romagna with a variation equal to an amount of 6.67% corresponding to the passage from 4.50 units up to 4.80 units or equal to an amount of 0.30 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a variation equal to an amount of 6.52% corresponding to a variation from 4.60 units up to 4.90 units. Puglia follows with a variation equal to 6.52% corresponding to a variation from 4.60 units up to 4.90 units or equal to an amount of 0.30 units. At the end of the ranking is Molise with a variation equal to 0.00 units, followed by Sardinia with a value equal to -4.08% corresponding to a variation from 4.90 units up to 4.70 equal to an amount of -0.20 units. In last place is Valle d'Aosta with a value of -6.67% corresponding to a variation from 4.50 units to 4.20 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified as indicated below:

- *Cluster 1:* Lombardy, Marche, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Emilia Romagna, Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo;
- *Cluster 2:* Sicily, Puglia, Liguria, Campania, Calabria, Trentino Alto Adige, Basilicata, Lazio, Tuscany, Sardinia, Piedmont, Molise.

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We can note that the value of trust in the judicial system tends to be higher in the regions of Cluster 2 compared to the corresponding value of the regions of Cluster 1. In fact, if we order the two clusters from the point of view of the average, then we can notice that Cluster 2 > Cluster 1. We can see that Cluster 2 contains almost all the southern regions with the exception of Abruzzo. It therefore follows that generally in the southern regions the value of trust in the judicial system tends to be higher than the corresponding value in the northern regions. However, in Cluster 2 there are also non-southern regions such as Lazio, Piedmont, Tuscany, Liguria and Trentino Alto Adige. Since the two clusters are very heterogeneous from a socio-economic and geographical point of view, it follows that clustering is not very efficient from a grouping point of view. And then we set $k=3$ to obtain a more efficient representation. Optimizing with the Silhouette coefficient it follows that:

- *Cluster 1*: Lombardy; Veneto, Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta;
- *Cluster 2*: Campania, Sicily, Calabria, Puglia, Liguria;
- *Cluster 3*: Piedmont, Sardinia, Tuscany, Lazio, Molise, Trentino Alto Adige, Abruzzo, Emilia Romagna.

Considering the value of the average of the clusters we obtain the following ordering: $C2 > C3 > C1$. We can see that the leading order is made up of C2 or 4 southern regions and Liguria. These regions have the maximum value of trust towards the judicial system. Cluster 3 follows. Cluster 3 is very heterogeneous and brings together southern, central and northern regions. The regions of cluster 3 are also characterized by significant heterogeneity in terms of per capita income. The last cluster based on the average value of trust in the judicial system is made up of cluster 1 made up of a mix of regions in the Central Italy and North Italy.

Italian macro-regions. The value of trust in the judicial system grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. However, this value grew more in the southern macro-regions than in the northern macro-regions. The value of trust in the judicial system grew in Southern Italy by a value equal to 10.87% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.6 units up to a value of 5.1 units. This value also grew in Southern Italy with +8.51%, in Northern Italy and in the North-East with an amount equal to 6.82%, in Central Italy with a value of 6.52%, in the North-West with a value of +4.55%, and in the Islands with a value of 4.17%.

Predictions with machine learning algorithms. Below we consider the application of machine learning algorithms for predicting the value of trust in the judicial system. Eight different machine learning algorithms are compared. The algorithms are trained with 70% of the available data. The remaining 30% is used for the actual prediction. The algorithms are classified based on their ability to maximize the value of the R-squared and minimize the value of the statistical errors, i.e. Mean Absolute Error-MAE, Mean Squared Error-MSE, Root Mean Squared Error-RMSE. Rankings are created to evaluate the algorithms. The positioning of the algorithms in the various rankings is added up to determine a final payoff value. A ranking is drawn up based on this value. Obviously the lower score will be preferred to a higher one, as it represents a better position in the ranking. It is therefore possible to obtain the following ordering of the clusters:

- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 4;
- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 9;
- Tree Ensemble with a payoff value of 11;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 18;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 20;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 22;

- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 28;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore, by applying Random Forest Regression or the best predictor it is possible to identify the following predictions:

- Piedmont with a decreasing variation equal to -2.23% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.80 units up to a value of 4.69 units;
- Trentino Alto Adige with a decreasing variation corresponding to a variation of -0.29 units equal to a variation from 4.90 to 4.89;
- Veneto with an increase from an amount of 4.50 units up to a value of 4.56 or equal to an amount of +1.31%;
- Emilia Romagna with a decreasing variation equal to -2.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.80 units up to a value of 4.67 units;
- Lazio with a decreasing variation equal to -5.39 units corresponding to a variation from an amount of 5.10 units up to 4.83 units;
- Calabria with a decreasing variation equal to -1.24% corresponding to the passage from 5.10 units up to 5.04 units.

On average, the value of trust in the judicial system decreased by an amount equal to -1.80% corresponding to a variation from 4.87 to 4.78 units.

Conclusions. Confidence in the judicial system has grown in all Italian macro-regions. However, the value of trust in the judicial system remained constant in Tuscany and Molise between 2011 and 2022, while in the same period it decreased by 4.08% in Sardinia and by 6.67% in Valle d'Aosta. In general we can notice, through the clustering analysis, that the southern regions tend to have a higher level of trust in the judicial system than the northern regions. In particular, the rich and productive regions of the North-East, namely Lombardy, Veneto and Friuli Venezia Giulia, have low levels of trust in the judicial system. This condition is due to the fact that in economically efficient regions the intervention of the judiciary could be considered as a political obstacle to the efficiency of productive organisations. In fact, it is no coincidence that it is precisely the Northern regions that support the many Italian political movements that ask for a downsizing of the judiciary, and consider the judicial power to be profoundly influenced by politics. The same idea of a political use of the judiciary is proposed precisely by the political movements that are most widespread in the Northern regions. However, the fact that trust in the judiciary tends to decline with growth in per capita income could also suggest the need for faster judicial proceedings which are necessary in economies operating at high levels of efficiency. It is probable that a population that has greater levels of social capital, human capital, entrepreneurial ability, ethical orientation and socio-economic and cultural activism, may understand the intervention of the State as an impediment with respect to the action of private-market coordination and extra-regulatory. On the contrary, regions with low per capita incomes, characterized by structural under-production and under-employment, with a significant diffusion of legal conflicts among the population, may need greater intervention from the judiciary, and therefore develop a sense of trust in towards the judiciary. It should be considered that the growth in per capita income also indicates a greater protagonism of the population in the economy and therefore could highlight the ability of private individuals to reach out-of-court resolutions of disputes. This option may appear scarcely practicable in the southern regions both for cultural reasons and for operational capacity.

In summary, the increase in trust in the judicial system is certainly a positive fact, as it demonstrates the presence of a growth in the effectiveness of the system. However, the distribution of this trust demonstrates the presence of areas of the country, especially the northern ones, which would probably be ready to experiment with a new dimension of dispute resolution which increasingly sees the participation of private individuals in the face of a reduction in the role of the judiciary.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Regioni	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	4,5	4,4	4,4	4,3	4	4,2	4,1	4,4	4,7	4,8	4,8	4,8
Valle d'Aosta	4,5	4,4	4,2	4	3,9	4,2	4,2	4,2	4,5	4,8	4,6	4,2
Liguria	4,7	4,7	4,6	4,4	4,3	4,4	4,2	4,6	4,6	5	4,8	4,9
Lombardia	4,4	4,2	4	4	3,7	4	4	4,3	4,5	4,6	4,5	4,5
Trentino-Alto Adige	4,6	4,4	4,4	4,2	4,1	4,4	4,6	4,4	4,8	4,9	4,8	4,9
Veneto	4,2	4	3,9	3,4	3,4	3,4	3,6	4	4,3	4,6	4,5	4,5
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	4,4	4,3	4	4	3,8	4	4,3	4,4	4,6	4,5	4,5	4,6
Emilia-Romagna	4,5	4,1	4,3	4,1	3,8	4,1	4,1	4,2	4,6	4,8	4,9	4,8
Toscana	4,8	4,2	4,4	4,4	4,1	4,2	4,3	4,3	4,8	4,9	4,7	4,8
Umbria	4,6	4,2	4,1	4,1	3,4	4	4,1	4,3	4,7	4,8	4,7	4,8
Marche	4,3	4	4,2	3,8	4	4	3,7	4,1	4,4	4,6	4,6	4,7
Lazio	4,6	4,4	4,3	4,4	4	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,7	4,7	4,8	5,1
Abruzzo	4	4,5	4,4	4,2	3,9	4	3,9	4,3	4,7	4,8	4,8	4,8
Molise	4,7	4,6	4,4	4,3	3,9	4	3,9	4,4	4,7	4,7	4,7	4,7
Campania	4,7	4,8	4,4	4,8	4,3	5	4,4	4,8	4,9	5	5,2	5,3
Puglia	4,6	4,6	4,5	4,4	4,4	4,4	4,2	4,7	5	4,9	5	4,9
Basilicata	4,5	4,6	4,3	4,1	4,5	4,4	4,3	4,3	4,8	4,9	4,9	5,1
Calabria	4,8	4,6	4,3	4,4	4,6	4,7	4,8	4,9	4,8	5,2	5,2	5,1
Sicilia	4,8	4,9	4,7	4,6	4,3	4,7	4,3	4,6	4,9	4,9	5	5,2
Sardegna	4,9	4,3	4,4	4,3	4,1	4,1	4,3	4,3	4,6	4,8	4,9	4,7

Macro-regioni	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	4,4	4,2	4,2	4	3,7	4	4	4,3	4,5	4,7	4,6	4,7
Nord-ovest	4,4	4,3	4,2	4,1	3,8	4,1	4,1	4,3	4,5	4,7	4,6	4,6
Nord-est	4,4	4,1	4,1	3,8	3,7	3,9	3,9	4,1	4,5	4,7	4,7	4,7
Centro	4,6	4,2	4,3	4,3	4	4,3	4,3	4,4	4,7	4,8	4,7	4,9
Mezzogiorno	4,7	4,7	4,5	4,5	4,3	4,6	4,3	4,6	4,9	4,9	5,1	5,1
Sud	4,6	4,7	4,4	4,5	4,3	4,6	4,3	4,7	4,9	5	5,1	5,1
Isole	4,8	4,8	4,6	4,5	4,2	4,6	4,3	4,5	4,8	4,9	5	5

	ANN	PNN	Simple Regression Tree	Gradient Boosted Tree
R^2	-0,328017794	0,482880756	-0,125	-0,434955226
Mean Absolute Error	0,285671145	0,207792208	0,291666667	0,285134846
Mean Squared Error	0,15788656	0,065665936	0,15625	0,133408536
Root Mean Squared Error	0,397349418	0,256253655	0,395284708	0,365251332
	Random Forest Regression	Tree Ensemble Learning	Linear Regression	Polynomial Regression
R^2	0,624817677	0,437009901	-0,498538822	-2,99043
Mean Absolute Error	0,127549082	0,178468624	0,424604741	0,59524
Mean Squared Error	0,03334954	0,076455445	0,213911792	0,47279
Root Mean Squared Error	0,182618564	0,276505778	0,462505991	0,68760

Algoritmo	R^2	Mean Abs	Mean Squ	Root Mean	Totale
Random Forest Regression	1	1	1	1	4
PNN	2	3	2	2	9
Tree Ensemble Learner	3	2	3	3	11
Gradient Boosted Tree	6	4	4	4	18
Simple Regression Tree	4	6	5	5	20
ANN	5	5	6	6	22
Linear Regression	7	7	7	7	28
Polynomial Regression	8	8	8	8	32

	2022 Prediction	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	4,80	4,69	-0,11
Trentino Alto Adige	4,90	4,89	-0,01
Veneto	4,50	4,56	0,06
Emilia Romagna	4,80	4,67	-0,13
Lazio	5,10	4,83	-0,27
Calabria	5,10	5,04	-0,06
Media	4,87	4,78	-0,09

Rank	Regioni	2022
1	Campania	5,3
2	Sicilia	5,2
3	Lazio	5,1
4	Basilicata	5,1
5	Calabria	5,1
6	Liguria	4,9
7	Trentino-Alto Adige	4,9
8	Puglia	4,9
9	Piemonte	4,8
10	Emilia-Romagna	4,8
11	Toscana	4,8
12	Umbria	4,8
13	Abruzzo	4,8
14	Marche	4,7
15	Molise	4,7
16	Sardegna	4,7
17	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	4,6
18	Lombardia	4,5
19	Veneto	4,5
20	Valle d'Aosta	4,2

Rank	Regioni	2011	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Abruzzo</i>	4,00	4,80	0,80	20,00
2	<i>Basilicata</i>	4,50	5,10	0,60	13,33
3	<i>Campania</i>	4,70	5,30	0,60	12,77
4	<i>Lazio</i>	4,60	5,10	0,50	10,87
5	<i>Marche</i>	4,30	4,70	0,40	9,30
6	<i>Sicilia</i>	4,80	5,20	0,40	8,33
7	<i>Veneto</i>	4,20	4,50	0,30	7,14
8	<i>Piemonte</i>	4,50	4,80	0,30	6,67
9	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	4,50	4,80	0,30	6,67
10	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	4,60	4,90	0,30	6,52
11	<i>Puglia</i>	4,60	4,90	0,30	6,52
12	<i>Calabria</i>	4,80	5,10	0,30	6,25
13	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	4,40	4,60	0,20	4,55
14	<i>Umbria</i>	4,60	4,80	0,20	4,35
15	<i>Liguria</i>	4,70	4,90	0,20	4,26
16	<i>Lombardia</i>	4,40	4,50	0,10	2,27
17	<i>Toscana</i>	4,80	4,80	0,00	0,00
18	<i>Molise</i>	4,70	4,70	0,00	0,00
19	<i>Sardegna</i>	4,90	4,70	-0,20	-4,08
20	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	4,50	4,20	-0,30	-6,67

